

FOREIGN LANGUAGE BORROWINGS IN MODERN ENGLISH.

Abdullaeva S.M.

Teacher of Uzbek State World Languages university
Tashkent, Uzbekistan
sevara_a_98@mail.ru

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This article touches upon the topic of borrowings in English. The author gives a generalized description of the historical periods of the English language and analyzes some words. Based on the conducted research, it was established that foreign language borrowings are one of the important types of enrichment of the vocabulary of the English language. However, despite the high percentage of borrowings, English cannot be classified as a language of international origin. The topic of borrowings in the development of the English language is very relevant. One of the ways to expand your vocabulary is to borrow from other languages of the world. For example, Old English had in its lexical composition borrowings from two languages: Latin and Celtic. Middle English had in its lexical composition borrowings from French and Scandinavian languages. In the Early Modern English period, borrowings occurred during the Restoration era. The words were borrowed from Italian (these were mainly words related to the visual arts, music, theater), Spanish, Dutch (these were words related mainly to navigation and painting). Subsequently, the range of languages from which borrowings came into English continued to expand. Borrowings came from Russian, German; languages of the Middle East, languages of India and Australia. These borrowings are studied by such learned linguists as K.P. Ivanova, A.N. Smirnitsky, L.F. Zalesskaya. The history of the English language is traditionally divided into three periods: Old English - the period from the beginning of written monuments (7th century) to the end of the 11th century, Middle English - from the beginning of the 12th century to the 15th century, New English - from the 16th century to the present day.

The first population of the British Isles was a non-Indo-European tribe of Britons, whose level of material culture belongs to the Neolithic (Late Stone Age). The next settlers were the Celts. In 55 BC, Julius Caesar launched a campaign against the British Isles. This first campaign was not successful, but in the following year 54 BC he managed to achieve success, impose tribute on the Celts and take hostages. Roman rule in Britain lasted until the 5th century AD. After the departure of the Roman legions, Britain was captured by the Germans. By the end of the 6th century, the Germans finally settled throughout Britain, with the exception of the mountainous regions. The language of the conquerors

influenced the language of the indigenous population. The most ancient Germanic inscriptions (starting from the 3rd century AD) used a runic alphabet, consisting of 24 characters containing only vertical and oblique lines. Only two Old English monuments of runic writing have been found. These are inscriptions on a stone cross near the village of Gutwell, and a whalebone box, decorated with carvings and bordered with an inscription telling about legendary creatures. Christian missionaries introduced the Latin alphabet to England.

In Old English, there are two layers of borrowings from Latin: the oldest layer, which includes words borrowed by Germanic tribes from the Romans even before the resettlement to Britain and after the resettlement - from the Celts; the second layer is words related to religion, associated with the introduction of Christianity, which began in 597. The first layer of borrowings consisted of words related to trade, agriculture, as well as the names of objects of material culture: Win - wine (from Latin *utilitas* > present wine, Pound - pound (from Latin *pondo*) > present pound, Mynet - coin (from Latin) > present time - mint. The Germanic tribes knew only apples from fruits; other fruits and vegetables became known to them later from the Romans: Rege - pear (from Latin *1 piece*), > present time react Pluwe - plum (from Latin *rspiz*).) > present plam Bete - beet (from Latin *beta*) > present beet. The ancient Germans were engaged in animal husbandry and knew well what milk was. However, the Romans introduced them to the preparation of butter and cheese: Ciese - cheese (from Latin *caseus*) > present. time cheese Butere - butter (from Latin *butyrum*) > present buttert The Romans also learned about spices: Mint - mint (from Latin *heat! a*) > present mint Words related to cooking were borrowed: Cucene - kitchen (from Latin *coquina*) > present tense kitchen Cuppe - cup (from Latin *sirra*) > present tense - sir.

During their reign in Britain, the Romans built good, powerful roads, their name - *strata via* - paved road - was taken by the Germans from the Celts: the Old English *strit* originally meant road, and since settlements began to appear along the roads, *strit* acquired the meaning "street". The Romans also built fortified forts and camps - *castra*. This word has become part of various geographical names: Lancaster (in the English dialect - *caster*), Manchester (in the dialect *caKco-ceaster* > present Chester).

The capital of England, London, also retains traces of Celtic origin in its name. London is called by the Celts: *Llyn-dun* fortress by the river. The Romans remade it into *Londinium*. In Scottish dialects, the Celtic word *loch* is preserved - lake, which became part of the names of many lakes in Scotland of Celtic origin.

The name of the western part of Britain, in which the remnants of the Celtic tribes settled, is Weals - Wales. Iron has been mined in Wales since ancient times, and the name of this metal, cap, is also of Celtic origin.

Borrowings from the Latin and Celtic languages came into general use, obeyed the word-formation, grammatical and phonetic laws of the Old English language, and became indistinguishable from the desired words.

During the Middle Period, the vocabulary of the English language underwent significant changes. The Scandinavian and Norman conquests had a huge impact, which caused an influx of large amounts of borrowing. Massive borrowing led to an abundance of synonyms, often displacing original words. The vocabulary was also replenished using internal resources through affixation and compounding. Historical conditions of development. The Middle English period in the history of England is characterized by two major historical events that left their mark on the further development of the English language. This is due primarily to the following historical and linguistic factors.

There were no sharp social differences between the speakers of Scandinavian dialects and the Anglo-Saxon population. Already from the 9th century, a mixed population formed in the area of Danish law. Initially hostile relations between the Scandinavians and Anglo-Saxons gradually became more friendly. The absence of social contradictions between the conquerors and the local population contributed to the rapid assimilation of the two nationalities. English and the Scandinavian languages were so close that people who spoke them could easily understand each other, so direct contact was possible between them.

Contact between the English and French languages, which coexisted on the same territory, takes on different forms due to the differences between them. After the conquest of England by William the Conqueror, the country began a long period of bilingualism. The feudal nobility uses French, and the bulk of the population uses English. Over time, the French language ceases to be the native language of the ruling class, it falls out of use in everyday life, but continues to be artificially maintained as the state language, the language of high society, the court, judicial institutions and the church. English is seen as uplandish and rude. There is much evidence in Middle English literature that without knowledge of French it was impossible to advance in society, and a person who did not speak French is not told of, that is, he was not taken into account. Thus, French has always been separate from English. It influenced the English language, but did not mix with it. In the field of vocabulary, Scandinavian influence differs from French in its wide coverage of a wide variety of semantic areas. Everyday words penetrate from

Scandinavian into English, including even pronouns (English - they) and function words (for example, the English preposition till). But to the greatest extent, the depth of Scandinavian influence is characterized by the impact of Scandinavian dialects on the grammatical structure of the English language. Mixing with Scandinavian dialects contributed, first of all, to accelerating the process of weakening unstressed endings and the collapse of the system of declension and conjugation that had begun in the English language. In the process of forming a mixed English-Scandinavian dialect, a uniform grammatical system should have been developed. Morphological differences between English and Scandinavian were more significant than differences in vocabulary. If it is not difficult to identify the Scandinavian stein - "stone" with the English stan (not to mention such correspondences as dom rock, Scandinavian dom-r; - Old English fisc - fish, Scandinavian fisk - r; b and so on), then the inflection system is similar identification of grammatical affixes was impossible.

As a result of the collision of two different systems of inflection, neither of them was preserved; both of them, with the mutual contact of languages, became simplified and underwent numerous analogous transformations. The dependence of morphological processes in English on Scandinavian influence is confirmed by the fact that this process occurred especially intensively in the area of Danish law, where it was completed more than a hundred earlier than in other areas. Since the bulk of the population spoke English, the English forms won out for the most part. In other words, the winner was the English language, the Scandinavian dialects dissolved in it. So, the Scandinavian influence on English morphology did not consist in the fact that Scandinavian forms were borrowed, but in the fact that crossing contributed to a change in the grammatical structure of the English language. The Scandinavian influence on the syntax of the English language was also significant.

French influence in the field of morphology is limited to word formation. A significant number of word-forming elements - suffixes and prefixes - have penetrated into English from French. This influence was possible because the English language borrowed a significant number of words from French, including derivative words.

Scandinavian borrowings are so closely intertwined with old Anglo-Saxon words that it is often difficult to determine whether we have a borrowing or simply a semantic change in an English word caused by Scandinavian influence. A striking example of such a change is the word of the Old English dream > Middle English drem - a dream in which the form is English, but the meaning is clearly

Scandinavian, since in Old English this word meant “triumph, joy” while the meaning of “sleep, dream” was characteristic only of Scandinavian languages. Borrowings from Scandinavian languages led to the formation of Scandinavian-English etymological doublets. This happened in cases where both etymological parallel lexical units were preserved - the Scandinavian and English words. The difference between the Scandinavian and English forms of the word was used for semantic differentiation, resulting in two different, although etymologically identical, or related words.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the history of the English language is inextricably linked with the history of England. When the Romans left the British Isles in 410, the Latin language left with them. The true inhabitants of the island (the Britons) continued to use Celtic languages. The ancestors of modern Englishmen did not waste time. In 449, the Germanic tribes of the Angles, Saxons and Jutes began their first raids on the islands. The language of the conquerors, to which only a handful of Celtic words were added, is now called Anglo-Saxon. In the 6th century, missionaries brought Christianity to England. Latin words borrowed from priests immediately found their way into the spoken language. The changes that occurred from the 6th to the 15th centuries were natural and were not supported by any theory. People tried to speak the same way as their neighbors spoke, and everyone who knew how to write at least tried to capture the sounds of their speech on paper. With the spread of literacy, the English language slowed its change, but it continues to change to this day. The ease of use of the rules, as well as the richness of the vocabulary, which continues to expand, has allowed the English language to become an international language of communication over the past half century.

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